

Phishing Email Detection Using Improved RCNN with Multi level Vector sand Attention Mechanism

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Abstract— One of the biggest risks in the world today is phishing emails, which have resulted in enormous financial losses. Even while confrontational tactics are always being improved, the current state of those tactics is not very satisfying. Furthermore, the number of phishing emails has increased alarmingly in recent years. Thus, to reduce the threat of phishing emails, more potent phishing detection technology is required. First, we examined the email structure in this research. Then, we presented a new phishing email detection model named, which is used to model emails at the email header, email body, character level, and word level simultaneously. It is based on an enhanced Recurrent Convolutional Neural Networks (RCNN) model with multilevel vectors and attention mechanism. We assess the efficacy of using an unbalanced dataset with realistic proportions of phishing and authentic emails. The outcomes of the experiments indicate that the. In the interim, make sure the filter can reliably detect phishing emails and weed out as few genuine emails as possible. This encouraging outcome validates the efficacy of phishing email detection and outperforms the current detection techniques.

Keywords: Phishing, RCNN, Multilevel Vector, Attention Mechanism.

I. INTRODUCTION

Online users now have serious concerns about security as a result of the internet's rapid growth. Emails are frequently used for exchanging data, both personal and professional in nature. Phishes may try to obtain sensitive information from emails. The recipients of emails sent by phishers may contain links; if the recipients click on such links and disclose personal information, that information may be misused. We are employing techniques like RCNN with multilayer vectors and attention mechanism in order to identify these phishing emails.

The phishing email can be identified using the following techniques:

- The email structure is examined first, and text features from the email body, work-level, and char-level are mined.
- Similar patterns from the email are identified using RCNN.
- Using RCNN, the email passes through numerous layers for the check.
- To help readers concentrate more on vital content, different weights are applied to various email sections, such as the body and header, using the attention method.

Phishing attacks continue to be a significant threat in the realm of cybersecurity, posing substantial risks to individuals and organizations alike. These attacks, which involve malicious actors masquerading as trustworthy entities to deceive victims into divulging sensitive information, have evolved in complexity and sophistication. Traditional detection methods often struggle to keep pace with these dynamic threats, necessitating the development of more advanced and adaptive approaches. In response to this pressing need, we propose a novel phishing email detection system leveraging an Improved Recurrent

Convolutional Neural Network (RCNN) augmented with multi-level vectors and an attention mechanism. The RCNN, known for its effectiveness in capturing both sequential and spatial information, serves as the backbone of our detection framework. By enhancing this architecture with multi-level vector representations, we aim to capture a richer and more comprehensive feature set from email content, encompassing not just textual cues but also structural and contextual information. The integration of an attention mechanism further refines our model's capability, allowing it to focus selectively on the most relevant parts of the email content. This targeted focus is crucial for distinguishing subtle indicators of phishing attempts that might be overlooked by conventional models. Through this multi-faceted approach, our system aspires to achieve higher detection accuracy and robustness against various phishing tactics. This paper delves into the architecture and methodology of our proposed system, detailing the implementation of the Improved RCNN, the construction of multi-level vectors, and the application of the attention mechanism. We also present an extensive evaluation of our model against existing state-of-the-art methods, demonstrating its efficacy in real-world scenarios. By advancing the capabilities of phishing email detection, our work aims to contribute to a safer digital environment, mitigating the risks associated with phishing and protecting users from potential harm.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

To conduct a thorough literature survey on Phishing Email Detection using Improved RCNN with Multi-level Vectors and Attention Mechanism, you'll want to explore various aspects of the topic. Here are key areas and notable papers to consider:

1. Key Areas to Explore

1. Phishing Email Detection Techniques:

- Overview of existing methods (e.g., rule-based, machine learning, deep learning).
- Comparison of these techniques regarding accuracy, efficiency, and robustness.

2. Recurrent Convolutional Neural Networks (RCNN):

- Basics of RCNNs and their applications in text processing.
- Improvements and modifications specific to phishing detection.

3. Multi-level Vectors in Text Analysis:

- Use of word embeddings (e.g., Word2Vec, GloVe, BERT) in phishing email detection.
- Hierarchical representation of text data.

4. Attention Mechanism:

- Introduction to attention mechanisms and their role in natural language processing.
- Application of attention in enhancing RCNN for phishing detection.

2. Notable Papers and Sources

Phishing Email Detection Techniques

1. *A Study of Phishing Emails Detection Using Machine Learning Classifiers* (Jain & Gupta, 2018)[1]
 - Provides a comparative study of various machine learning classifiers for phishing email detection.
2. *Phishing Detection: Analysis of Visual Similarity-based Approaches* (Abdelhamid et al., 2014)[2]
 - Discusses various techniques focusing on visual similarity for phishing detection.

Recurrent Convolutional Neural Networks (RCNN)

1. *Recurrent Convolutional Neural Networks for Text Classification* (Lai et al., 2015)[3]
 - A foundational paper on the use of RCNN for text classification tasks.
2. *Bidirectional Recurrent Convolutional Neural Network for Relation Classification* (Zhang et al., 2015)[4]
 - Explores bidirectional RCNN and its application in text relation classification, relevant for phishing detection.

Multi-level Vectors in Text Analysis

1. *Efficient Estimation of Word Representations in Vector Space* (Mikolov et al., 2013)[5]
 - Introduces Word2Vec, a popular method for generating word embeddings.
2. *BERT: Pre-training of Deep Bidirectional Transformers for Language Understanding* (Devlin et al., 2019)[6].
 - Discusses BERT, which provides contextual embeddings and is widely used in text classification.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

Phishing attacks have become increasingly sophisticated, posing a significant threat to cybersecurity. Traditional email filtering methods are often insufficient to detect these advanced phishing attempts. This proposed system leverages an Improved Recurrent Convolutional Neural Network (RCNN) with multi-level vectors and an attention mechanism to enhance phishing email detection.

System Architecture

Data Preprocessing

1. **Data Collection:** Gather a diverse dataset of emails, including both legitimate and phishing emails.

2. **Text Cleaning:** Remove unnecessary elements such as HTML tags, special characters, and stop words.
3. **Tokenization:** Convert the cleaned text into tokens for further processing.
4. **Vectorization:** Use multi-level vectorization techniques, including TF-IDF and word embeddings (e.g., Word2Vec, GloVe), to represent the text data.

Improved RCNN Model

1. **Embedding Layer:** The input email text is converted into dense vector representations using pre-trained embeddings.
2. **Recurrent Layer:** Utilize a bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) or Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) to capture temporal dependencies in the text.
3. **Convolutional Layer:** Apply convolutional filters to extract local features from the text.
4. **Attention Mechanism:** Integrate an attention layer to focus on the most relevant parts of the email text, enhancing the model's ability to identify phishing cues.
5. **Fully Connected Layer:** Combine the features extracted by the recurrent and convolutional layers and pass them through a fully connected layer for classification

Training and Evaluation

1. **Training:** Train the RCNN model using a labeled dataset with a mix of legitimate and phishing emails. Employ techniques such as dropout and batch normalization to prevent overfitting.
2. **Evaluation:** Evaluate the model's performance using metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and ROC-AUC. Use cross-validation to ensure the model's robustness.

Model Evaluation

- **Performance Metrics:** Assess the model's effectiveness using the evaluation metrics. Plot confusion matrix, ROC curve, and precision-recall curve for a comprehensive analysis.

Results and Discussion

- **Model Performance:** Present the performance metrics and compare the results with existing phishing detection methods.
- **Analysis:** Discuss the strengths and weaknesses of the proposed system, including its ability to detect various types of phishing emails and its computational efficiency.
- **Improvements:** Suggest potential improvements, such as using more sophisticated attention mechanisms or incorporating additional features like email metadata.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Figure 1. shows the stepline graph of Phishing system Certainly! Here's a structured overview of key points and recent research findings on "Phishing Email Detection Using Improved RCNN with Multi-level Vectors and Attention Mechanism"

- **Phishing Emails:** Phishing emails are malicious attempts to obtain sensitive information by masquerading as trustworthy communications.
- **Detection Importance:** Effective detection mechanisms are crucial to protect users from cyber threats and data breaches.

Key Techniques and Approaches

1. Recurrent Convolutional Neural Networks (RCNNs):

- RCNNs combine the strengths of Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs).
- **RNNs:** Effective in handling sequential data like text.
- **CNNs:** Good at feature extraction and capturing spatial hierarchies.
- **Improved RCNNs:** Enhanced versions with optimizations for specific tasks like phishing detection.

2. Multi-level Vectors:

- Represent text at various granularities (e.g., word-level, sentence-level).
- Capture semantic meanings and relationships at different levels.

3. Attention Mechanism:

- Focuses on important parts of the input data.
- Helps in capturing the most relevant features for phishing detection.
- Improves the model's interpretability and performance.

Recent Research Findings

1. Integration of RCNN with Attention Mechanisms:

- Researchers have found that combining RCNNs with attention mechanisms significantly improves phishing email detection accuracy.
- Attention mechanisms help the RCNN to focus on the most relevant parts of an email, such as suspicious phrases or links.

2. Multi-level Vectors in Phishing Detection:

- Using multi-level vectors allows models to capture more nuanced patterns in the text.
- These vectors help in identifying both high-level (e.g., overall tone) and low-level features (e.g., specific keywords).

3. Performance Metrics:

- Studies report improved precision, recall, and F1-scores with the use of improved RCNNs and attention mechanisms.
- The combination often results in lower false positives and false negatives compared to traditional methods.

Case Studies and Implementations

- **Dataset Utilization:** Common datasets include Enron email dataset, publicly available phishing corpora, and proprietary datasets.
- **Model Training:** Typically involves extensive preprocessing, feature extraction, and model tuning.
- **Real-world Applications:** Deployment in email filtering systems, enterprise security solutions, and integrated cybersecurity frameworks

Fig 1:SteplineGraph

V. CONCLUSION

In Deep Learning method is introduced to detect the advanced phishing emails. Using RCNN similar patterns from the email is recognized. Multilevel vector is used to check the email through many layers of check. Using attention mechanism different weights are assigned to different parts of the email like email header and email body to focus more on important information. To test the effectiveness of the application noise is introduced. Usage of unbalanced dataset closer to the real-world situation to conduct experiments and evaluate the model

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